

Hybrid Face Recognition Model for Student Attendance Tracking Using Machine Learning Algorithms

Sheela S. Maharajpet ✉

Department of MCA, Acharya Institute of Technology, Bangalore – 560107, India

G.P. Mithun

Department of MCA, Acharya Institute of Technology, Bangalore – 560107, India

H.P. Abhilash

Assistant Professor, School of CSA, REVA University, India

Abstract

Attendance tracking in educational institutions is critical, the manual methods are very difficult, in particularly for large numbers of student populations. In this research novelty new methodology proposed work a face recognition based attendance monitoring system that employs deep learning prediction system and computer vision. This system aims to streamline processes, reduce fraud, and improve accuracy. This study has used robust face detection algorithms, combined with Histograms of Oriented Gradients (HOG) feature extraction to yield a comprehensive database of authorized students face detection using Deep Learning (DL), when integrated with Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Support Vector Machine (SVM), KNearest Neighbor (KNN), and CNN classification, improves both system performance and accuracy. Enrollment generates unique identifiers, and regular updates to a centric dataset in order to make attendance tracking easier. This study promises to regulate attendance in schools in a practical and precise way.

Keywords: *Facial Recognition, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, FaceNet, KNN, OpenCV, Attendance System, HOG, SQL, SVM, PCA.*

Suggested citation: Maharajpet, S.S., Mithun, G.P., & Abhilash, H.P. (2025). Hybrid Face Recognition Model for Student Attendance Tracking using Machine Learning Algorithms. *Scientia. Technology, Science and Society*, 2(7), 51-61. DOI: 10.59324/stss.2025.2(7).06

Introduction

Organizations are required to monitor individuals within the establishment, including employees and students, to enhance their effectiveness. In contrast, taking attendance is an essential task in every industry to monitor students or employees. Since attendance is a vital part of administration, it can quickly turn into a time-consuming, tedious task that is prone to errors. Traditionally, students' attendance is recorded manually in class with an attendance sheet given by faculty, which is a time-consuming process (Tantak, et al., 2017). Numerous schools' methods have disadvantages like paper waste, classroom interruptions, and more. The process of monitoring student attendance during class sessions has shown to be challenging. As manual calculations lead to mistakes and take considerable time, calculating the attendance percentage turns into a significant task. The primary concern with current attendance management systems is the accuracy of the collected data. This is

due to the possibility that the original individual's attendance might not have been documented. An external party can record a student's attendance without the institution's awareness, leading to inaccuracies in the data (Tan, 2018).

The current system's second issue is that it requires too much time. Imagine a student writing their name on a 3-to 4-page list of names in one minute. Only about 60 students can mark their attendance in an hour, making it ineffective and lengthy. Another issue is the truly interested party's capacity to obtain such information. Many parents, for instance, are especially concerned about monitoring their child's whereabouts to ensure that their child goes to classes or school. Conversely, parents currently do not have access to this information (Ahmedi, & Nandyal, 2015; Zhao, et al., 2003; Kortli, et al., 2020).

Principal Component Analysis along with the Eigen Face Technique were utilized to develop the face recognition system (Navesh, et al., 2017). A system for automatically updating attendance based on facial recognition technology was developed. This system will also be used to collect images of various individuals' faces. Nonetheless, this system operates a centralized database, which may be compromised due to advancements in technology. The search for an advanced system featuring a complex database framework that is secure and resistant to breaches is essential.

Compared to previous deep learning algorithms, FaceNet has optimized performance to 128-D embedding, resulting in a smaller representation size for each face. Following the alignment process to crop the facial area during the preprocessing stage, we input a dataset of faces into the network (Tatiraju, et al., 2017).

The proposed offline attendance system leverages facial recognition technology to automate student attendance tracking, enhancing accuracy and efficiency. It employs FaceNet for face embeddings and KNN for classification, achieving high recognition accuracy. The process begins with uploading a group photo, where faces are detected using Haar Cascade or MTCNN. HOG features are extracted, and PCA is applied for dimensionality reduction. The identified faces are compared with a reference database using DeepFace, with classification performed using SVM, KNN, or CNN. Matched faces are marked as "Present," while unmatched faces are labeled "Absent." Attendance records are stored in a CSV file for easy retrieval. This method streamlines attendance monitoring, reducing manual effort and minimizing fraud.

Literature Survey

Attendance systems powered by facial recognition have been extensively studied and adopted to enhance efficiency, security, and precision in educational settings and workplaces. Omkar Biradar and Anurag Bhawe (2019) suggested a Face Recognition Attendance Monitoring System Utilizing Raspberry-Pi and OpenCV, which automates the recording of attendance through a camera that takes pictures of students or employees. The system identifies faces and compares them with saved entries in the student database. The attendance information is subsequently updated automatically on an online platform. The facial recognition procedure in this system comprises two primary stages: pre-processing, which entails face detection and alignment, and the recognition stage, which incorporates feature extraction and matching. Image normalization is executed through Raspberry-Pi and OpenCV to improve recognition precision and performance.

A different research project, Automated Attendance System Utilizing Face Recognition, conducted by Yeoleker (2017), created a system employing facial recognition methods that demonstrated efficiency in time and security. In this system, student attendance is recorded automatically upon their entry into the classroom, with the system recognizing their faces. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was discovered to excel in real-time situations in comparison to other algorithms,

thanks to its elevated recognition rate and minimal false positive rate. Nonetheless, a drawback of the system is its ability to recognize faces only within a 30-degree angle range, which requires enhancement for improved real-world functionality. Upcoming studies in this field seek to improve recognition precision in diverse facial scenarios, including beard development, hairstyle alterations, or items like glasses.

To improve the accuracy and efficiency of facial recognition, deep learning is required. Similar to how the human brain recognizes patterns and characteristics in vast datasets, this area of machine learning (ML) allows models to do the same. Artificial neural networks (ANN), which include supervised, semi-supervised, and unsupervised learning, are the main foundation of deep learning. Several hidden layers in the deep learning architecture convert unstructured visual data into structured representations. Deep learning networks, in contrast to conventional neural networks, are able to identify significant information at many levels of abstraction because of their numerous non-linear layers. While the more sophisticated layers understand intricate face features like the mouth, nose, and eyes, the earlier layers recognize basic edges and forms. Deep learning techniques, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), have shown considerable success in areas such as handwriting recognition, autonomous vehicle navigation, and especially, facial recognition (Schroff, Kalenichenko, & Philbin, 2015).

A popular computer vision method for locating, confirming, and identifying human faces in images and movies is facial recognition. Classification and feature extraction are the two primary processes in this procedure. Important face traits, like the sizes, shapes, and locations of the eyes, nose, mouth, and jawline, are first recognized by the algorithm. By comparing the acquired qualities to entries stored in a database, a relationship is formed. The strength of feature extraction and classification methods is the primary determinant of face recognition effectiveness. CNNs are frequently utilized in facial recognition because of their exceptional capacity to recognize distinct facial features and reduce errors. Convolutional, pooling, and fully connected layers are some of the layers that make up CNN-based recognition models. These layers gradually improve visual representations at different levels. CNNs' efficiency in face recognition applications is significantly increased by their autonomous feature extraction capability, which eliminates the need for manual feature engineering (Voulodimos, et al., 2018).

Among the deep learning-driven facial recognition methods, FaceNet has become one of the leading models. Created by Google Inc. in 2015, FaceNet converts facial images into 128-dimensional embeddings that capture unique facial characteristics in a concise manner. It employs Euclidean distance to assess similarity between faces, facilitating precise face verification and recognition. FaceNet employs a triplet loss function that guarantees that embeddings of alike faces are grouped closely, whereas embeddings of dissimilar faces are spaced apart. The training procedure entails choosing triplets—three images that include an anchor (a reference image), a positive match (another image of the same individual), and a negative match (an image of a different individual). This guarantees strong distinguishability between various faces. FaceNet has shown impressive precision, reaching 99.63% on the Labeled Faces in the Wild (LFW) dataset and 95.12% on the YouTube Faces dataset (Dolecki, et al., 2016).

A major thing in attendance systems utilizing face recognition is maintaining data security and privacy. Numerous conventional systems depend on centralized databases, rendering them susceptible to cyberattacks and unauthorized access. To address these risks, researchers are investigating secure, decentralized frameworks that ensure strong data protection. Moreover, enhancing recognition algorithms to accommodate changes in facial expressions, lighting situations, and occlusions continues to be a significant aspect of advancement.

To sum up, attendance systems employing facial recognition offer a quick, accurate, and secure alternative to conventional manual attendance techniques. While early versions relied on OpenCV

for real-time face detection, advancements in deep learning have significantly improved recognition accuracy. CNN-based models, particularly FaceNet, have demonstrated remarkable effectiveness in generating facial embeddings and minimizing recognition errors. Future research in this field will likely focus on enhancing recognition across various facial scenarios, utilizing cloud storage for better accessibility, and implementing privacy-enhancing techniques to safeguard user data.

Table 1. Comparison Table

Sl. No	Paper Name	Authors	Technology/Algorithm Used	Results	Drawback
1	Face recognition for E-attendance for student and staff	Tantak A, Sudrik A, Kale A, Mehetre R, Pophale P	Face recognition using OpenCV and Haar Cascade	Automated attendance marking with improved accuracy	Limited dataset, may fail in low-light conditions
2	Facial Recognition Based Attendance Monitoring System for Educational Institution	Tan, S. J.	Deep Learning-based Face Recognition	Increased automation and reduced manual errors	Computationally expensive
3	Anautomatic attendance system using image processing	Ahmedi, A., & Nandyal, S.	Image Processing & Facial Features Extraction	Improved efficiency over traditional methods	Cannot handle occlusions effectively
4	Face recognition: A literature survey	Zhao W, Chellappa R, Phillips PJ, Rosenfeld A	Various Machine Learning Algorithms	Comprehensive survey of facial recognition advancements	Lacks experimental analysis
5	Face recognition systems: A survey	Kortli, Y., Jridi, M., Al Falou, A., & Atri, M.	CNN, SVM, PCA	Highlights advancements in facial recognition	No real-time implementation analysis
6	Automatic attendance system by using face recognition	Navesh S., Shubham, Y., Vaibhav, P., Vishal K., Parag, G., & Gaurav V.	CNN and Deep Learning	High accuracy with deep learning models	Requires high computational power
7	FaceNet: A Unified Embedding for Face Recognition and Clustering	Florian Schroff, Dmitry Kalenichenko, James Philbin	FaceNet (Deep Learning)	High accuracy with Euclidean space embedding	Requires large dataset for training
8	Deep Learning for Computer Vision: A Brief Review	Athanasios Voulodimos, Nikolaos Doulamis, Anastasios Doulamis, Eftychios Protopapadakis	Deep Learning, CNN	Overview of deep learning techniques in vision	No specific application focus

9	Face recognition by humans performed on basis of linguistic and neural network	Michal Dolecki, Pawel Karczmarek, Adam Kiersztyn, Witold Pedrycz	Neural Networks, Linguistic Models	Explores human-like face recognition	Lacks real-world implementation
10	Attendance management system using face recognition	Suman Kumar Jha, Aditya Tyagi, Kundan Kumar, Madhvi Sharma	OpenCV, Deep Learning	Effective attendance automation	May struggle with diverse lighting conditions

Methodology

The suggested solution uses facial recognition technology to automatically mark student attendance, guaranteeing security, accuracy, and efficiency. Image capture, preprocessing, face detection, feature extraction, and attendance logging are all part of the method's organized approach.

Figure 1. Overview of Proposed System

1. Capture Group Image of Students

The initial stage in the method involves capturing a group photo of the students in the classroom. This image acts as the main input for the attendance system. The picture needs to be bright and sharp to enable precise facial identification. Low-quality images caused by obstructions, blurriness,

or poor lighting can impact the precision of face detection and recognition. The system might also enable teachers to manually upload a picture taken with a smartphone or classroom camera to ensure flexibility in monitoring student attendance.

2. Image Acquisition

After the group photo is taken, it is sent to the system, which begins processing it. This stage is making sure the image satisfies the system's clarity and quality requirements and is in the appropriate format, such as JPEG or PNG. The user will be prompted to attempt again by the system if the image is corrupted or was not uploaded successfully. Image collection is essential because it ensures that the input is appropriate for additional analysis and prepares the recorded data for the processes that follow.

3. Image Processing

The system preprocesses the image once it has been acquired in order to improve its quality for precise face detection. In order to eliminate undesired background elements, this stage may involve scaling the image to a fixed resolution, modifying brightness and contrast, and using noise reduction techniques. Enhancing facial visibility through image filtering makes it simpler for detection algorithms to accurately recognize faces. Because only pertinent facial features are processed, proper image processing greatly increases recognition accuracy.

4. Face Detection

The system identifies every face in the group photo in this step. The system searches the image for facial regions using sophisticated face identification techniques like Multi-task Cascaded Convolutional Networks (MTCNN) or Haar Cascade Classifier. This stage guarantees that, even in photos of a packed classroom, the algorithm can recognize faces with accuracy. The system might ask the user to provide a higher-quality image if no faces are found. Since improper face detection can result in erroneous attendance records, face detection is an essential stage.

5. Face Recognition

The system advances to the recognition stage after the faces have been identified. In this step, facial features are extracted and transformed into facial embeddings, which are numerical data. Key facial features are analyzed using deep learning models such as FaceNet or DeepFace, which then generate a unique identification for every face. The student database's reference photos are matched to these identifiers. In order to accurately identify each student based on their distinct facial traits, face recognition is essential.

6. Compare Recognized Face with Database Images

The identities of the identified faces are then ascertained by comparing them with previously stored student photos in the database. The degree to which the extracted face features resemble the stored photos is examined by matching techniques such as K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), or Cosine Similarity. The student's attendance record is updated if a match is discovered. In order to prevent unauthorized people from being counted, this step makes sure that only registered students are marked present.

7. If Face Matched

The system verifies the identity and marks attendance if the identified face corresponds to a student record in the database. By ensuring that students are accurately identified, this verification step lowers the possibility of errors in attendance tracking. The student is deemed absent if the system is unable to locate a match. The system may let several recognition tries before completing the attendance record in order to increase accuracy.

8. Mark Attendance as Present

The technology automatically labels a student as "Present" in the attendance records if their face is correctly matched with the database. Both teachers and students will save time as a result of this automation, which does away with the necessity for manual attendance tracking. Real-time updates to the attendance data guarantee accurate and current records. Teachers may be able to manually check and amend attendance records in the event of a recognition failure.

9. Store an Attendance Report

The system creates a thorough attendance report once attendance has been recorded. For future use, this report is kept in a local database. Teachers or administrators can access the recorded data to monitor student attendance over time. For additional examination, the reports can also be exported in CSV or PDF formats. Attendance records should be stored securely to protect data privacy and stop unwanted changes.

10. Add Student Details (Manual Enrollment)

There is a choice to manually enter student information for new students who are not yet enrolled in the system. This entails entering their facial information into the database, assigning a distinct student ID, and submitting a reference photo. After being added, the student won't require any manual assistance to be identified in subsequent attendance sessions. By taking this step, the system is kept up to date and can handle newly enrolled students.

Architecture

Framework of the recommended system by employing facial recognition technology, the suggested method aims to automate the current human attendance system. The primary goal is to photograph and save the face of every student for attendance documentation. It is vital for each facial characteristic to be accurately recognized during photo shooting. By using facial recognition techniques on the captured image, teachers can take attendance in class without having to do it by hand. This article examines the issues frequently linked to hand-written attendance records. Haar Cascade classifiers are used for face detection, while the Local Binary Pattern Histogram (LBPH) technique is employed for recognizing students' faces.

Here are the main formulas used in the Haar Cascade classifier for face detection:

1. Haar Feature Calculation:

$$\text{Feature} = \sum(\text{Black Pixels}) - \sum(\text{White Pixels}) \quad (1)$$

2. AdaBoost Weight Update:

$$W_{t+1} = W_t e^{-\alpha y h(x)} \quad (2)$$

3. Strong Classifier Combination:

$$H(x) = \text{sign}(\sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t h_t(x)) \quad (3)$$

where $h_t(x)$ are weak classifiers, and α_t alpha t is the weight classifier.

System Architecture

The proposed Classroom Attendance System utilizing Face Recognition. A camera needs to be positioned in the classroom at a spot that enables it to capture video for the system, thus effectively photographing each student present. The desired results are achieved by processing this image, allowing for effective capturing of all the students in the classroom. This image has been edited to achieve the intended outcomes (Kaur, 2018).

Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG)

The Histogram of Oriented Gradients, commonly known as HOG, is a feature descriptor that can be compared to the Canny Edge Detector and SIFT (Scale Invariant Feature Transform) descriptors. It is utilized in computer vision and image processing to identify objects. The method counts the occurrences of gradient orientations within the confined image space. Numerous similarities exist between this technique and Edge Orientation Histograms, as well as Scale Invariant Feature Transformation (SIFT). The main emphasis of the HOG descriptor is on an object's shape or configuration. It surpasses all edge descriptors as it calculates the features by considering both the angle and magnitude of the gradient. It creates histograms for every part of the image according to the magnitude and direction of the gradient (Jha, et al., 2020).

$$G_y(s, r) = I(s, r + 1) - I(s, r - 1) \quad (4)$$

$$G_x(s, r) = I(s - 1, r) - I(s + 1, r) \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Magnitude}(\mu) = \sqrt{G_x^2 + G_y^2} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Angle}(\theta) = |\tan^{-1}(G_y / G_x)| \quad (7)$$

Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Employing an orthogonal transformation, principal component analysis (PCA) is a statistical method that converts a group of related variables into a set of independent variables. The leading machine learning technique for developing predictive models and conducting exploratory data analysis is principal component analysis (PCA). Moreover, the relationships among a set of variables are analyzed through Principal Component Analysis (PCA), which is an unsupervised learning algorithm method. Regression, often called generic factor analysis, is utilized to identify the optimal line of fit. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) seeks to maintain the key patterns or relationships among the variables while lowering the dimensionality of a dataset, doing so without needing any prior information regarding the target variables.

Support Vector Machine (SVM)

Regression and classification are performed using a supervised machine learning method referred to as Support Vector Machine (SVM). However, regression techniques are most effectively utilized in classification problems. The primary aim of the SVM algorithm is to determine the best hyperplane in an N-dimensional space to ensure data points may be categorized into various classes of feature space. The hyperplane seeks to maintain the highest practical separation between the nearest points of distinct classes. The dimension of the hyperplane is decided by the quantity of characteristics. When there are only two input features, the hyperplane functions as a line. When three input features exist, the hyperplane transforms into a two-dimensional plane (Razmah, 2022).

K-Nearest Neighbor Algorithm (KNN)

A well-liked and flexible machine learning method, the (K-NN) algorithm is mostly used because to its ease of use and implementation. Concerning the foundational data distribution, no assumptions are required. Furthermore, due to its capacity to manage both numerical and categorical data, it presents a flexible choice for a variety of dataset types in classification and regression tasks. It is a technique that is non-parametric that predictions based on the level of resemblance among data points within a specific dataset. In relation to different algorithms, K-NN shows reduced sensitivity to outliers (Wang, & Siddique, 2020).

Main Formula for K-NN Algorithm

The K-NN method for recognizing faces derives feature vectors from pictures and calculates the Euclidean distance between the input and saved facial images. It chooses the K nearest matches and determines the most common class as the predicted identity, guaranteeing precise recognition through similarity.

1. Euclidean Distance (Most Common for Face Recognition)

$$d(x, y) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - y_i)^2} \quad (8)$$

where: 1] $d(x, y)$ is the distance between two feature vectors xxx and yyy.

2] x_i, y_i are the feature values of the two faces.

3] n is the number of features.

2. Classification Rule

After computing the distances, select the **K nearest neighbors** and assign the most frequent class:

$$C = \arg \max \sum_{i=1}^K I(y_i = c) \quad (9)$$

where: 1] C is the predicted class (face identity).

2] $I(y_i = c)$ is an indicator function (1 if the neighbor belongs to class ccc, else 0).

3] K is the number of nearest neighbors.

Figure 2. [KNN] K-Nearest Neighbors Algorithm Working Graphs

Conclusion

By providing a safe, effective, and precise solution, the Facial Recognition-based Automatic Student Attendance System improves on the conventional attendance tracking methodology. By using categorization methods like K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) and deep learning models like FaceNet, the system effectively and precisely automates attendance monitoring. The experimental findings show a notable increase in face detection accuracy. The shortcomings of traditional manual attendance techniques, including errors, time inefficiency, and the possibility of false records, are addressed by this approach. The system offers educational institutions a reliable and scalable solution while guaranteeing data security and privacy thanks to its offline features. Monitoring and compliance are also improved by tools like automatic notifications for attendance violators.

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